

Quark Masses Mixing – 8 Theory

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June 19, 2021

Abstract:

In contrast to the previous paper about the subject which was mere computational, not in the spirit of the 8 theory which emphasize understating rather than numerical results, an additional take will be provided on this mind boggling problem of quark mass mixture. Using the main equation of the 8T will be the subject of that analysis, alongside the primordial function of coupling constants as additional tool for making the idea more solid.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.10)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

In the 8-theory thesis, it was proven that the arbitrary variations partitioned and discretized vanish into matter. What is not specified is which family of so-called quarks is presenting itself in the process. Since we calculated the quark masses series and derived that they are scalar multiples of decreasing order, the implicit idea is that there is a morphism, scalar in nature, between each family. We are leaving the actual angles of the mixing outside in this paper, absurd as it sound, as the emphasis is on why such a phenomena could accrue at the first place. Nature is devising in increasing amounts so we go from heavy families such as (T-B) which is really the first in order, toward much lighter families such as the (U-D) which is really the third in order. If we generate an amount of energy and accelerate fermions toward each other that is synonymous with creating higher amount of arbitrary variations. Since all we have is curvature that is part of one manifold, there could be mixtures of curvatures of different orientation or different amounts. Similar to how there could be mixtures of net variations in the coupling constants series.

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.12)$$

Gravity itself is such a mixture due to its spin two trait.

$$\left[2N^2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow [(2N(g)) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} \quad (1.13)$$

So if nature is going down and decreasing in higher magnitudes of divisors from one family to the next, we are doing the opposite at acceleration of fermions into one another and creating mixtures of arbitrary amount of curvatures or going from lower to higher. It is just an idea of course, the subject is still far from understood. Future papers will attempt to analyze it in different angles as well. If there is only one angle or a discrete set of angles in which the mixing accrue, there must be a reason to extract it from theory and reason why it is that angle, just like we did with the coupling series.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)